

MONITORING AUXETIC STRUCTURE WITH FBG SENSOR

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Abstract. Auxetic materials are a particular class of materials which present a negative Poisson ratio (NPR). This means that once they are stretched, they expand in the directions orthogonal to the applied load. The dual behaviour occurs during compression tests. Due to this characteristic, they present many interesting properties like increased resistance to fracture indentation and shear stress, lower crack propagation rate, synclastic behaviour, and the ability to tune their porosity by applying stress. Because of these properties, auxetic materials are gaining the attention of researchers. Their applications are diverse, ranging from automotive and aerospace to medicine and seismic applications. Because of their application potential, it is important to find an effective way to monitor their condition during use. Fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors are widely used in structural health monitoring (SHM) applications. They are particularly attractive due to their unique properties, such as multiplexing capability, resistance to electromagnetic interference, high measurement accuracy, chemical inertness that enables operation in harsh environments, and their very small size. However, due to the novelty and unique geometry of auxetic materials, monitoring them with FBG sensors presents challenges. In this work, we investigate the possibility of monitoring auxetic materials using FBG sensors.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metamaterials are a class of materials able to show behaviours extremely uncommon in nature. The study, which is considered the starting point for the history of metamaterials, is the article published in 1968 by Veselago [1]. In this work, the theoretical possibility of obtaining materials with a negative refractive index is shown. Only in 1996, Pendry et al. [2] defined a process for producing this kind of material. Building on this, the concept of metamaterials was extended to various applications. Therefore, nowadays metamaterials are classified into acoustic, electromagnetic or mechanical based on their peculiar characteristics [3]. This work focuses on auxetic materials. These are a class of mechanical metamaterials that present a negative Poisson ratio. From a practical point of view, it means that when they are stretched, they expand in the direction orthogonal to the applied load. On the other hand, during compression, they collapse transversely. The first auxetic material was observed by Lakes [4]. Thanks to this special behaviour, auxetic materials present other interesting properties. Increased shear resistance, in fact, shear modulus is

equal to [5]:

$$G = \frac{E}{2(1 + \nu)} \quad (1)$$

where G is the shear modulus, E is the Young modulus, and ν is the Poisson ratio. It is possible to notice that if ν approaches -1, the shear modulus tends to infinity. Another interesting property is an increased resistance to indentation. Under the action of the indenter, a normal material reacts by spreading in the direction perpendicular to the applied load. Conversely, the same load applied to an auxetic material cause a flow of the material towards the impact zone. Furthermore, it is possible to relate the indentation resistance with Poisson ratio [6]:

$$H \propto \left[\frac{E}{(1 - \nu^2)} \right]^\gamma \quad (2)$$

where H is the hardness and γ is a variable which is assumed equal to 1 for uniform pressure distribution, and equal to $2/3$ for Hertzian indentation. Also in this case, it is possible to see that if ν tends to -1, the hardness of the materials tends to infinity. It is also reported that auxetics exhibit an increased resistance to fracture [7]. In addition, they present a synclastic behavior [8]. It means that once they are subjected to an out-of-plane bending moment, they exhibit a dome shape. Conventional materials in the same situation demonstrate a saddle shape. Finally, it is reported that due to their shape, they can act as filters with variable permeability [9]. Thanks to their peculiar properties, they have possible applications in many fields. In the aerospace sector, they can be used to produce seat backs that increase the comfort and safety of the user [10]. Moreover, they can be used to create morphing airfoils [11] or a system to attenuate vibration noise [12]. Besides, they are useful for impact absorption systems [13]. Many applications are also possible in the biomedical field. For example, they are studied for the production of orthosis [14], or stents [15]. In addition, a research group has already investigated the possibility of using auxetic cells combined with a conventional structure to design new prostheses with enhanced bone integration [16]. Their use in tissue engineering applications is also explored [17]. In the case of constructions, they can be used for acoustic [18] and heat [19] insulation, or for protection in seismic applications [20]. Furthermore, auxetics can be exploited in automotive for impact absorption [21], seat comfort improvement [22], and jounce bumper enhancement [23]. Other interesting applications include textile [24], protective gear for both sports [25] and work [26], as well as sensors [27]. For applications related to aerospace, automotive and construction fields, monitoring is fundamental. Among monitoring techniques, Fibre Bragg grating sensors emerge for their high accuracy, high sensitivity, light weight, small dimensions, real-time response, multiplexing ability, immunity to electromagnetic field and chemical inertness [28]. These sensors are composed of an optical fibre with some zones in which the refractive index is periodically modulated. These periodic structures, thanks to the diffraction phenomenon, reflect with high selectivity one wavelength (please see Fig.1).

Figure 1: FBG scheme which shows the structure of the sensor and its behaviour.

Once these sensors are stretched or compressed, the periodicity of the inscribed structures changes; consequently, the reflected wavelength varies, a positive shift for stretching and a negative for compression. It is possible to connect the measured variation with the deformation applied using this formula [29]:

$$\lambda_B = 2n\Lambda \quad (3)$$

in this case, λ_B represent the wavelength of the reflected wave, n is the effective refractive index of the core, and Λ represents the periodicity of the grating. Since the refractive index is sensitive to changes in temperature, the measured shift is also a result of the system in which the sensor is positioned. This implies that FBG sensors can be used to measure temperature. As a consequence, during strain measurement, the effect of temperature must be compensated. In contrast, for temperature measurement, it is necessary to ensure that the sensor is not subject to a varying strain.

This paper aims to investigate the possibility of using FBG sensors for monitoring the behaviour of metamaterial structures efficiently. Furthermore, the influence of sensors on the behaviour of these structures will be explored. In fact, this topic is not deeply investigated in the literature. Just three relevant articles on this topic have been found[30, 31, 32].

The paper is organised as follows. Firstly, the materials and methods section shows how the specimens are designed and which mechanism they use to obtain auxeticity. Then it explains how they are produced and how FBG sensors are attached. Subsequently, the experimental setup is presented. Next, the data elaboration method is introduced. After that obtained data are presented, and finally considerations of the measured data are presented in the conclusion.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Specimen

The phenomenon of auxeticity can result from several distinct structural mechanisms. The main ones are re-entrant geometries, chiral and antichiral geometries, perforated geometries, and rotating polygonal geometries. For this experiment, two of those were selected, specifically, a re-entrant configuration (Fig. 2a) and a rotating square geometry (Fig. 2b).

Figure 2: Designed auxetic structure.

The former is a structure composed of ribs, in which some ribs are oriented inward. The latter arrangement is made by squares connected on their vertices. All these geometries were designed using the CAD software Siemens NX, then the model was converted to a triangle mesh and saved in STL format, so that it can be read and used by the internal software of the 3D printer. The dimensions of the specimen are reported in Tab. 1.

Geometry	Length	Width	Thickness
Re-entrant	220 mm	74 mm	2mm
Rotating square	140 mm	50 mm	2mm

Table 1: Specimens dimensions

After the design process, two specimens were produced for each type. For the production process it was used a multi-jet printing (MJP) device present in the rapid prototyping laboratory of IMP PAN. MJP, also known as multi-jetting (MJ), is an additive manufacturing technique. In this process, droplets of a photoreactive material are deposited on the printing bed and solidified with ultraviolet light. To manufacture samples the "3D Systems ProJet 3500 HD Max" 3D printer was used. The single thickness of the layer produced with this technology (MJP) is 16 μm at a resolution of 1600 DPI. In this case, two different materials were used; the first one is wax, which acts as a support material for the printing process. As a building material for the printing process, VisiJet M3-X was used. Experimental research has been carried out in the past [33] and the results showed that the static tensile strength of that material was 54 MPa (taking into account different directions of printing). The operational temperature for the elements printed from M3-X material should not exceed 80°C. Once the specimen is produced, the wax is removed using an oven. Finally, two FBG sensors are attached to the surface of the sample. One specimen was used per auxetic type. To attach the sensors, the same photo-reactive polymer was used as a glue to fix the optical fibre. The procedure for embedding the sensors was as follows: after positioning the sensor in the intended location, very thin layers of liquid M3-X material were applied to the sample surfaces in contact with the sensor. The sample was then exposed to UV light at a power equivalent to the UV lamp used during 3D printing (Fig. 3). The sensors were positioned forming a cross on the specimen (Fig. 4). Each sensor was placed centrally, with the grating carefully embedded inside a pore of the structure. This resulted in four specimens: two containing sensors and two without.

Figure 3: FBG sensors attachment process.

Figure 4: Experimental set-up and optical fibre(s) with FBG sensors position.

2.2 Testing protocols

All the produced specimens were tested. They were subjected to increasing tension till the rupture. The specimens were anchored to the testing machine with particular care to avoid the fibre being pinched in the machine jaws. Tests on a tensile machine were conducted under conditions of force increase over time. This value was determined based on previous experience with additively manufactured samples using MJP technology. Due to geometric considerations, a force increase parameter of 1000 N/min was assumed. To measure the effective deformation of the specimen, an extensometer was added to compare its measurement with that of the sensor. The base of the extensometer was 50 mm. For each sample, a different surface was used. For the re-entrant, the surface was 20 mm², while for the Rotating square, 123 mm²; these differences result from their complex geometry. Four specimens were tested: a re-entrant sample with sensors, a re-entrant sample without sensors, a rotating-square sample with sensors, and a rotating-square sample without sensors. The tests were performed in the following order: rotating square without sensors, re-entrant without sensors, rotating square with sensors, and re-entrant with sensors.

2.3 Data analysis

Data collected by the machine extensometer and interrogator are then elaborated using Matlab to extract deformation and applied stress, and then plotted to compare the behaviour of the specimens with and without the sensor and the deformation measurement made by the extensometer and the FBG sensors. Furthermore, the strain, measured by the horizontal FBG, is plotted to evaluate the auxetic behaviour. From the machine, elongation and force are measured to obtain information about stress and strain these formulas were used:

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A} \quad (4)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{L}{L_0} \quad (5)$$

where σ is the stress, a is the area of the specimen, L is the displacement and L_0 is the extensometer base length. On the other hand, from the interrogator, wave shifts are collected for each sensor. To obtain information about the deformation, a MATLAB script was created to identify the reference value for the sensor, and then, using it, the strain was calculated with the following equation:

$$\epsilon = \frac{\lambda B - \lambda B_0}{\lambda B_0} \quad (6)$$

Where ϵ is the strain, λB is the measured Bragg wavelength and λB_0 is the reference value for Bragg wavelength.

3 RESULTS

In this section, the results of the presented experiment are described. They are organised into three subsections: the first one demonstrates that the presence of the sensors does not affect the mechanical behaviour of the specimen. The second one compares the strain measurement recorded by the extensometer with the one registered by the FBG sensor to investigate the agreement between these two measurements. Finally, the horizontal deformation is compared with the vertical deformation. For the FBG sensor, vertical and horizontal are used according to the scheme presented in Fig. 4.

3.1 Stress-strain behaviour

In this section, data related to the stiffness of the specimens are analysed. To do this, two plots are built. The former represents the comparison of the stress-strain curve related to the re-entrant geometry with and without sensors, Fig. 5a. The latter represent the same data but are related to the rotating square geometry Fig. 5b. To generate these graphs, the force was measured using the machine's force sensor, while deformation was measured with an extensometer.

Figure 5: Stress-strain graphs for re-entrant (a) and for rotating square (b).

The curves presented here do not show a significant difference. In particular, it can be noted that in one case, the sample with the FBG shows a lower stiffness, and in the second, it is higher. The calculated difference is calculated using this formula:

$$\Delta E_{\%} = \frac{E1 - E_{FBG}}{E1} \quad (7)$$

Where $\Delta E_{\%}$ is the percentage difference in stiffness, $E1$ is the Young modulus of the specimen without sensors and finally E_{FBG} is the stiffness of the specimen with embedded sensors. The calculated difference for the re-entrant is 10.24% for the rotating square is -26.20%. This is a demonstration that the FBGs do not affect the mechanical behaviour of the auxetic matrix. These minor variations can be attributed to small differences in sample geometry, small local effects related to sensor attachment, or to effects related to the printing method and post-printing process. In addition, it is possible to notice that the re-entrant structure shows a higher stiffness compared with the rotating square structure. The reason for the presented behaviour can be the connection between cells of the re-entrant structure, which is less dense, but the load is sustained homogeneously on the entire cell. Instead, in rotating square geometry, the load is sustained only on the connectors between cells, making the specimen shape easier to deform.

3.2 FBG sensors vs extensometer

Here, it is inquired about the accordance between measurements recorded by the extensometer and by the vertical FBG sensors. In Fig. 6a and Fig. 6b, measurements related to re-entrant and rotating square geometries are presented, respectively. Due to the absence of multiplication by the coefficient, it is quite difficult to compare the two sets of data, because the strain measured

by the extensometer is much higher than the measurement of the FBG sensor. To compare the shapes of the two signals, each signal was standardised using the z-score method. Specifically, the mean value of each signal was first subtracted from all its data points, centring the signal around zero. Then, the resulting values were divided by the signal's standard deviation. This standardisation procedure preserves the relative patterns and trends within each signal while removing differences in absolute amplitude and offset, allowing a direct comparison of the overall shape of the signals, regardless of their original scale. In the former one, the measurements related to the re-entrant geometry are compared Fig. 6c. In the latter, data from the rotating square geometry is reported Fig. 6d.

Figure 6: Comparison between measurements made by extensometer and vertical FBG sensor with raw data on re-entrant (a) and rotating square (b) geometry, and with standardised data on re-entrant (c) and rotating square (d) geometry.

For raw data, the extensometer measures a global, average, strain over a relatively long gauge length, while the FBG sensor records a local strain only in the small region where the fibre is bonded. The absolute values can differ, depending on local material behaviour, bonding quality, and sensor position. This behaviour was expected because it was already noticed in another work [34]. In the first case, apart from a delay, it is possible to state that the two signals have a similar shape. The shift in time is because the systems are not interconnected, so they are started manually, and there is a different starting time. In the second case, the shapes of the signals are less overlapping, but it is possible to state that they are quite similar. The similarity between the data collected by the extensometer and the vertical FBG sensors shows that the measurements made by the FBG sensors on auxetic materials are reliable.

3.3 Analysis of horizontal and vertical sensor measurements with FBG sensors

The following graphs summarise the measurements made by vertical and horizontal FBGs. Data are normalised with respect to the maximum absolute value. In this case, this normalisation method has been chosen because to verify the auxetic behaviour of the specimen, it is necessary to evaluate the sign of the measurement. So with this method, we can compare the shape of the two curves without affecting the sign of the data. In Fig. 7a, results obtained on the re-entrant geometry are presented. In Fig. 7b, the rotating square data are presented.

Figure 7: Comparison between vertical and horizontal measurements on re-entrant (a) and rotating square (b) geometry.

It is possible to state that the normalised data are completely overlapping. Also, in this case, deformation in the horizontal direction follows the behaviour of the vertical direction. It must be noted that there is an agreement between the signs of the two measurements. It is important because it demonstrates that the sensors do not affect the auxeticity of the material.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this study highlights the potential of auxetic structures in various applications and underscores the importance of developing effective monitoring methods. Experimentally, it was shown that embedding FBG sensors does not affect the mechanical behaviour of the auxetic structures. Moreover, FBG sensors were able to effectively measure specimen deformation, as

evidenced by the agreement between the vertical FBG sensor measurements and the extensometer data.

Despite the magnitude differences in strain measurement, direct comparison with the extensometer measurements provides useful insights [34]. Additionally, comparisons of FBG sensor measurements in vertical and horizontal directions confirm that horizontal deformations correspond to the applied load, demonstrating the auxetic behaviour of the specimens. Importantly, the FBG sensors do not inhibit this behaviour.

This study represents a preliminary exploration of a relatively under-investigated area, with only three relevant articles [30, 31, 32] found in the literature. Future work will focus on embedding FBG sensors inside the auxetic matrix to further advance the monitoring of these structures.

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